

ELECTRONIC SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Health economic evaluation of colorectal cancer screening
policy in Flanders

1. Electronic Supplementary Material

1.1. Epidemiological estimates

We used the data from the yearly epidemiological reports from both the Belgian Cancer Registry (SKR) and the Centre for Cancer Detection (CvKO) to construct an adjusted full prevalence of CRC in the population of Flanders. This is analogous to calculating the expected distribution of cancers “if everybody was screened with a perfect test”. This takes into account that the number of clinically presenting cancers is not increasing with this hypothetical test. The graph below shows the age distribution of reported cases, and the smoothed adjustment.

Table 1: Distribution of reported cancer stages between participation groups

Distribution of reported CRC by stage and participation type	Participants	Interval cancers	non-Participants
CRC St. IV	4.60%	16.90%	23.80%
CRC St. III	11.40%	15.20%	21.40%
CRC St. II	9.70%	14.40%	19.90%
CRC St. I and 0	74.30%	53.50%	34.90%

Figure 1: Resulting prevalence curves before and after adjustments.

Figure 2: Diagram of transition probability estimation method.

To estimate the initial transition probabilities (within the undetected group) to progress through the states, we applied a methodology as described in the diagram above, and in section 2.1 in the article. Using the estimated prevalences per year and state ($\chi_{i,j}$ in the diagram) we can solve backwards from Stage IV for the required progression rates from the previous state ($\theta_{i,j}$ for progressions, $\gamma_{i,j}$ for the remainder). Building on the assumption that the adjusted prevalence as above is correct, the diagram can be filled in through a backwards induction process starting with CRC St. IV. Because there are only *known outflows* from this state (deaths, detections, treatments) we can solve the no-transition rate (1-outflows), and the inflow from CRC St. III to make up the difference. At this point the set of outflows of CRC St. III are full, and the steps can be traced back. We do this for multiple years to take an average transition rate.

This process is somewhat naïve, in that it expects transition rates to remain stagnant over time. This could be altered with drift parameters, should enough information be available to estimate these. A benefit of this method is that the resulting transition rates give the model a sense of gravity towards the current state of CRC in the population. I.e. These rates tend to produce a long-run state not too dissimilar from the current state, if no changes in screening occur. Another benefit stems from the ease in which this process could be automated with yearly reported data, meaning that the government could easily use this tool to make a new evaluation with future epidemiological data.

The resulting transition rates are shown in the table below.

Table 2: resulting transition probabilities within the undetected group.

Males						Females				
From	Healthy	Polyp. Ad.	CRC1	CRC2	CRC3	Healthy	Polyp. Ad.	CRC1	CRC2	CRC3
To	Polyp. Ad.	CRC1	CRC2	CRC3	CRC4	Polyp. Ad.	CRC1	CRC2	CRC3	CRC4
Age										
45	0.002	0.070	0.273	0.857	0.710	0.002	0.069	0.268	0.840	0.696
46	0.002	0.067	0.275	0.866	0.718	0.002	0.065	0.268	0.843	0.699
47	0.002	0.065	0.277	0.874	0.726	0.002	0.062	0.268	0.846	0.703
48	0.002	0.063	0.279	0.883	0.735	0.002	0.060	0.268	0.848	0.706
49	0.003	0.062	0.281	0.891	0.744	0.003	0.059	0.268	0.850	0.710
50	0.003	0.061	0.283	0.899	0.753	0.003	0.058	0.268	0.852	0.713
51	0.003	0.061	0.285	0.907	0.761	0.003	0.057	0.268	0.853	0.716
52	0.003	0.061	0.287	0.914	0.769	0.003	0.057	0.268	0.854	0.719
53	0.003	0.061	0.288	0.920	0.777	0.003	0.057	0.268	0.855	0.722
54	0.004	0.062	0.290	0.926	0.785	0.004	0.057	0.267	0.854	0.724
55	0.004	0.063	0.291	0.932	0.792	0.004	0.057	0.267	0.854	0.726
56	0.004	0.064	0.293	0.936	0.799	0.004	0.058	0.266	0.852	0.727
57	0.005	0.065	0.294	0.941	0.806	0.004	0.059	0.266	0.850	0.729
58	0.005	0.066	0.295	0.944	0.812	0.005	0.060	0.265	0.848	0.730
59	0.005	0.068	0.296	0.948	0.819	0.005	0.061	0.264	0.845	0.730
60	0.005	0.070	0.297	0.951	0.825	0.005	0.062	0.263	0.842	0.731
61	0.006	0.072	0.298	0.953	0.830	0.005	0.063	0.262	0.839	0.731
62	0.006	0.074	0.298	0.956	0.836	0.006	0.064	0.261	0.836	0.731
63	0.007	0.076	0.299	0.958	0.841	0.006	0.066	0.260	0.832	0.731
64	0.007	0.078	0.300	0.962	0.854	0.006	0.067	0.259	0.830	0.737
65	0.007	0.080	0.301	0.965	0.866	0.007	0.069	0.258	0.827	0.743
66	0.008	0.083	0.301	0.968	0.877	0.007	0.071	0.257	0.824	0.747
67	0.008	0.085	0.302	0.971	0.887	0.008	0.072	0.255	0.821	0.750
68	0.009	0.088	0.303	0.973	0.896	0.008	0.074	0.254	0.818	0.753
69	0.009	0.091	0.303	0.975	0.904	0.008	0.076	0.253	0.814	0.755
70	0.010	0.094	0.304	0.977	0.912	0.009	0.078	0.252	0.810	0.757
71	0.010	0.097	0.304	0.978	0.919	0.009	0.080	0.251	0.806	0.758
72	0.011	0.100	0.305	0.980	0.926	0.010	0.082	0.250	0.802	0.758
73	0.011	0.103	0.305	0.981	0.933	0.010	0.083	0.248	0.798	0.759
74	0.012	0.106	0.306	0.982	0.939	0.011	0.085	0.247	0.793	0.759
75	0.012	0.102	0.286	0.919	0.879	0.011	0.082	0.230	0.738	0.705

1.2. Screening rates

The screening participation is an important dynamic in this model, so we took care to create a methodology that accounted for sufficient real-world complexity. This started with designing two schedule matrices, as shown below.

Figure 3: Screen Wave Matrices for the Current (top) and Expanded (bottom) screening scenarios.

Fig. 2. These matrices show the logic behind the screening participation for the current and expanded screening scenarios. Blue indicates that this age does not participate in state screening. Green indicates a year-age combination where most people are invited to participate. Red means a year-age combination where people are less likely to be invited. A ripple can be seen in this structure, as a result of previous staggered expansions in the target screening demographic.

The next step was to estimate the invitation rates that correspond to the red/green year-age combinations as seen in the matrices above. To be able to freely change model any changes in the screening schedule, we estimated an invitation rate for scheduled years (green) and unscheduled years (red). Because a not-insignificant percentage is invited outside scheduled years, we incorporated this in the model. We fitted 3rd order polynomials to the data, stratified by age and schedule. We applied a ceiling to the maximum rates to never fall above or below observed rates. This same process was performed on the probability to participate in screening, conditional on being invited.

Figure 4: Invitation and Participation Rates

This two-step differentiation between invitation and participation allowed us to separate out two different dynamics. First, that invitations decrease with age (as more people opt out or are excluded for medical reasons), and also become less stratified according to the schedule. Second, that intrinsically people become more likely to participate as they age.

Using these three principles together (wave matrices, invitation rate, and participation rate) on past years allows to compare the resulting number of tests versus the reported number of tests (averaged over 4 years), as shown in the figure below.

Figure 5: Number of tests, predicted and reported.

Overall, the “retrodiction” tends to follow the actual pattern well. It tends to underestimate the peaks and overestimate the troughs, but to only a small amount. The net result is a slight underestimation of the number of tests of less than 5% on the short run. This results primarily from the overestimation of exclusions in the younger age groups, which is likely to become more accurate in the long run.

1.3. Input Costs and Disutilities in the Model

The following table shows the disutilities that have been applied to each health state. These disutilities are applied relative to the healthy utility score by age-year. The healthcare costs aggregated by specific health state are also shown, as is a comparison to the cost applied in the prior model [1]. The sources for these specified below the table. All costs are indexed to 2022 using the Healthcare costs index.

Table 3: Costs and disutilities

Disutilities and costs per health state, aggregated values						
Health State	Disutility	Ref.	Healthcare cost	<i>Prior Values*</i>	Ref.	
Ad. Polyp	0.065	[1]	n/a	<i>n/a</i>		
Unidentified CRC St. I	0.085	[1]	n/a	<i>n/a</i>		
Unidentified CRC St. II	0.085	[1]	n/a	<i>n/a</i>		
Unidentified CRC St. III	0.140	[1]	n/a	<i>n/a</i>		
Unidentified CRC St. IV	0.655	[1]	n/a	<i>n/a</i>		
Treatment CRC St. I	0.170	[1]	€ 15,263	€ 12,808	[1, 2]	
Treatment CRC St. II	0.170	[1]	€ 27,071	€ 22,716	[1, 2]	
Treatment CRC St. III	0.280	[1]	€ 33,251	€ 31,351	[1, 2]	
Treatment CRC St. IV	0.655	[1]	€ 39,634	€ 37,369	[1, 2]	
Follow-up years 1-4 CRC St. I	0.128	[1]	€ 9,730	€ 7,795	[1, 2]	
Follow-up years 1-4 CRC St. II	0.128	[1]	€ 7,349	€ 5,888	[1, 2]	
Follow-up years 1-4 CRC St. III	0.210	[1]	€ 4,733	€ 3,992	[1, 2]	
Follow-up years 1-4 CRC St. IV	0.655	[1]	€ 13,837	€ 11,669	[1, 2]	
Follow-up years >4 CRC St. I	0.064	[1]	€ 241	€ 202	[1, 2, 3]	
Follow-up years >4 CRC St. II	0.064	[1]	€ 241	€ 202	[1, 2, 3]	
Follow-up years >4 CRC St. III	0.105	[1]	€ 4,733	€ 3,992	[1, 2]	
Follow-up years >4 CRC St. IV	0.328	[1]	€ 13,837	€ 11,669	[1, 2]	
False positive result	0.021	[1]	n/a	<i>n/a</i>		
Colonoscopy	0.003	[1]	€ 241	€ 202	[3]	
Polypectomy	0.014	[1]	€ 540	€ 393	[3]	

[1] Pil, L., Fobelets, M., Putman, K., Trybou, J., & Annemans, L. (2016). Cost-effectiveness and budget impact analysis of a population-based screening program for colorectal cancer. *European journal of internal medicine*, 32, 72-78. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejim.2016.03.031

[2] Pacolet, J., De Coninck, A., Hedeboew, G., Cabus, S., & Spruytte, N. (2011). De medische en niet-medische kosten van kankerpatiënten. ISSN: 978-90-5550-481-7

[3] RIZIV Rijksinstituut voor ziekte- en invaliditeitsverzekering. NomenSoft. Available at: <https://www.riziv.fgov.be/webprd/appl/pnomen/Search.aspx?lg=N>.

1.4. Results: Total costs and benefits

The following tables show the resulting total costs and benefits between the three scenarios. Costs are separated between “screening costs” (programme costs), healthcare costs for all resulting treatments, and the societal costs (from lost labour production). These are shown in the deterministic case, the probabilistic average, and the standard error. Finally, these are also shown as a proportion to the person years in the model. The final table also shows the general breakdown of healthcare costs per scenario, into costs made for screening (FIT and fixed costs), colonoscopies (and polypectomies), cancer treatments, and follow-up costs. The last two categories are the main drivers of total costs.

Table 4: Total costs and benefits per scenario

Costs per scenario	Total (20 year, in Millions)			Average per year (in Thousands)			Avg. p.p.y.
	Det.	Prob. Avg.	St. Err.	Det.	Prob. Avg.	St. Err.	
Screening costs							
No Screening	0 M	0 M	(0.0)	0 K	0 K	(0.0)	0.0
Current Screening	75 M	79 M	(7.6)	3,404 K	3,781 K	(364.2)	0.6
Expanded Screening	79 M	84 M	(8.4)	3,594 K	3,991 K	(401.1)	0.6
Healthcare costs							
No Screening	4,817 M	5,102 M	(243.9)	219,049 K	242,973 K	(11615.7)	35.7
Current Screening	4,723 M	4,999 M	(2595)	214,703 K	238,034 K	(12359.4)	34.9
Expanded Screening	4,719 M	4,994 M	(260.4)	214,507 K	237,823 K	(12401.3)	34.8
Labour costs							
No Screening	13,509 M	19,418 M	(0.9)	614,046 K	924,668 K	(42.9)	135.7
Current Screening	13,456 M	19,337 M	(0.9)	611,618 K	920,813 K	(42.9)	134.9
Expanded Screening	13,453 M	19,335 M	(0.9)	611,518 K	920,705 K	(42.9)	134.8

Benefits per scenario	QALYs (total)			Per person-year		Life years (total)		
	Det.	Prob. Avg.	St. Err.	Det.	Prob. Avg.	Det.	Prob. Avg.	St. Err.
No Screening	79,073K	79,007K	(5175.4)	0.5474	0.5469	113,183 K	113,196 K	(5309)
Current Screening	79,266K	79,197K	(5184.3)	0.5487	0.5482	113,384 K	113,395 K	(5319)
Expanded Screening	79,274K	79,206K	(5184.7)	0.5488	0.5483	113,396 K	113,407 K	(5320)

Table 5: Breakdown of Healthcare cost per scenario and category

Cost breakdown per scenario	No Screening	Current Screening	Expanded Screening
Screening Costs	0.6%	2.0%	2.1%
Colonoscopies and polypectomies	2.6%	5.2%	5.3%
Treatment costs	49.5%	44.2%	43.9%
Post-Treatment costs	47.3%	48.7%	48.7%

1.5. Results: Sensitivity results

For the univariate sensitivity, we modelled several clusters of high-impact parameters as shown in the tornado diagrams below. This sensitivity is expressed in relative terms (i.e. a relative change in an input parameter, causing a relative change in either incremental costs or benefits). An effect of more than 100% in the opposite direction would change the ICER quadrant. In other words, a decrease of 100% in incremental benefits moves the base-case ICER to the eastern quadrant, and a decrease of 100% in incremental costs moves it to the southern quadrant. The combined effect of the incremental costs and benefits is shown in the Tornado graph on the next page.

Figure 6: Tornado Diagrams of incremental costs, benefits, and ICER.

The combined effect of the univariate sensitivity analysis is shown in the graph below. While computationally analogous to the ICER, the effects are shown as the cost saved per QALY gained. As an example, a *decrease* in the disutilities of CRC *decreases* the incremental benefits (leaving costs the same), meaning that the savings per QALY *increases*. Similarly, a 50% decrease in overall treatment costs comes very close to a decrease of 100% in costs saved per QALY. A change greater than -100% would indicate an ICER that is no longer cost saving (dominant).

Figure 7: Effects on costs saved per QALY.

Inputs and effects are shown in relative changes. Input parameters are increased (blue) / decreased (red) with 10, 25, and 50%. The magnitude of the effect is shown on the horizontal axis as %-change in incremental benefits (top graph) or incremental costs (Middle graph). The final graph shows the effect on the costs-saved per QALY. An increase of 100% means that the costs saved per QALY doubles, whereas a decrease of 100% means that the intervention is no longer cost-saving (dominant).

As a reference point: the model has constant returns to scale in terms of population size. This can be seen in the incremental benefits, where a decrease of 50% (deep red) reduces incremental benefits by 50%. Likewise, increasing the population by 50% (deep blue) increases incremental benefits by 50%. Using this as a reference point helps to contextualise the other parameter impacts. Lastly in final graph there is no change associated with population size to the actual cost/QALY. Note however that the base-case incremental costs are negative, so effects are mirrored in direction.

The multivariate probability analysis resulted in three ICER scatterplots, one for each scenario comparison. The first two scatterplots (Current screening versus No Screening, and Expanded screening versus No Screening) are highly similar to each other. The third scatter plot shows the comparison between Current and Expanded screening. In this comparison the incremental costs and benefits are understandably lower, but the benefits are also consistently positive.

Figure 8: Scatterplots for the comparisons between Current and No screening (top) and Expanded and No screening (bottom).

Figure 9: Scatterplot for the comparison between the Current and Expanded Screening scenarios.

